

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FORMATION OF YOUTH READING CULTURE

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Abstract. Formation and development of the reading culture of young people is one of the urgent issues today, and the role of innovative technologies in this process is incomparable. Digital technologies, in particular, electronic and audio books, online platforms, mobile applications, virtual and augmented reality (VR and AR) technologies are becoming an effective tool in increasing the interest of young people in reading books and facilitating the process of learning. In this article, the possibilities of engaging young people in reading with the help of technologies are analyzed, the positive and negative effects of technologies are studied.

The article highlights the opportunities that technology creates for young people's reading, and also examines the impact on their attitude to reading. Among the positive aspects, the creation of wide access to books through digital libraries and mobile applications, the opportunity to spend time reading in different conditions through audiobooks, the possibility of sharing ideas and giving recommendations on social networks and reading platforms are important. For example, in Uzbekistan, national platforms such as "ZiyoNET" portal and "Kitob.uz" serve as an important tool in increasing the interest of young people in reading. Digital libraries like this one allow to download and read books in a convenient form, which encourages young people to be in constant contact with books.

However, there are also negative effects of innovative technologies on the reading culture of young people. As a result of the use of technologies, there are risks such as a decrease in the ability to concentrate attention, an increase in dependence on technology, as well as a superficial acceptance of information. Reading through electronic devices often leads to speed reading and superficial thinking, which reduces the opportunity to fully benefit from the reading process. In order to eliminate such problems, it is important to teach young people to use technology effectively and moderately.

The article contains recommendations on improving the efficiency of using innovative technologies for youth reading and reducing the negative effects. It is emphasized that it is necessary to focus on improving digital literacy, developing time management skills, and restoring the traditional approach to reading. The conclusions presented in the article serve to increase the intellectual potential of young people and develop their reading culture through the rational use of innovative technologies.

Keywords: youth reading, innovative technologies, e-books, audiobooks, digital libraries, mobile applications, virtual reality, augmented reality, social networks, reading culture, digital literacy, attention control, technology addiction.

Introduction

In today's era of globalization and development of information technologies, the formation of the culture of reading and learning among young people is becoming an urgent issue. Innovative technologies play an important role in obtaining information and expanding the scope of knowledge of young people. In particular, projects aimed at increasing interest in reading using digital technologies, electronic libraries, mobile applications and virtual reality (VR) technologies

are being developed in Uzbekistan. This article analyzes the role and importance of innovative technologies in forming the reading culture of young people.

Formation and development of reading culture among young people not only increases their intellectual potential, but also serves to form a knowledgeable and mature society in the future. Nowadays, technologies are developing rapidly, and the possibilities of accessing and studying information are expanding. In this regard, the role of innovative technologies in the formation of reading culture among young people is of particular importance. This article discusses the use of technology, its advantages and disadvantages in promoting youth reading.

In Uzbekistan, the use of digital libraries and e-books serves as an important factor in increasing interest in reading among young people. For example, the electronic library service offered by the portal "ZiyoNET" includes educational materials from various subjects for students. Through the portal "ZiyoNET", young people have the opportunity to read and download books in digital form, which helps them gain knowledge quickly and conveniently (Karimov, 2019, p. 23). Also, national platforms such as "Kitob.uz" allow young people to get acquainted with the best examples of national and world literature (Usmanov, 2020, p. 15).

Technologies serve to increase interest in reading among young people. As living conditions and teaching methods change, young people are more interested in reading books in digital formats. Studies conducted in European countries show that the use of e-books among young people is increasing rapidly compared to traditional books (Smith, 2020, p. 45). At the same time, access to digital libraries and Internet resources makes the reading process even simpler.

Increasing interest in e-books and audiobooks among young people is one of the important means of attracting them to reading culture. Thanks to digital technologies, young people have the opportunity to read books anywhere and at any time. With the help of electronic books, students have the opportunity to store and use books in a convenient form, which expands the possibilities of spending time on reading (Karimov, 2019, p. 23).

Audiobooks, on the other hand, are very popular among young people, and they allow you to listen to books even when you are busy. Audiobooks play a big role in increasing interest in reading, especially while traveling, doing sports or doing housework. The project of audiobooks created by the National Library of Uzbekistan provides an opportunity for young people to learn comprehensive information and have it in a convenient way. According to the results of the survey, the majority of young people choose audiobooks, which makes the learning process more effective (Rasulov, 2021, p. 30).

In addition, the ability to save and review the material read through e-books and audiobooks encourages young people to read regularly. For example, through mobile applications, users can download and save books of their interest in electronic form. In this way, they can read or listen to several books at the same time, which significantly increases interest in reading (Azimov, 2018, p. 54).

The great thing about e-books and audiobooks is that they allow you to quickly absorb the content. For example, young people save a lot of time by memorizing or mastering a book of several hours in the form of an audiobook in a few minutes. Therefore, the widespread use of audiobooks among young people serves to increase the efficiency of their learning (Usmanov, 2020, p. 15).

Audiobooks and podcasts are a modern and convenient means of reading for young people, attracting them to read in different conditions - for example, on the road or while playing sports.

Through such technologies, young people have the opportunity to learn about the subjects they are interested in. The practice of creating audio books and providing them by the National Library of Uzbekistan is widely adopted and arouses great interest among young people (Rasulov, 2021, p. 30).

As young people's interest in digital books grows, e-books and audiobooks serve as an effective means of engaging in reading. Reading media in the form of audiobooks and podcasts is a modern trend for young people. According to data, according to the results of a survey conducted in 2021, 60 percent of young people chose audiobooks (Johnson, 2021, p. 32). This allows you to spend time reading, especially when you are on the move or playing sports.

With the development of modern technologies, the role of mobile applications and online platforms in increasing interest in reading among young people has increased significantly. Through these technologies, the process of reading books is more convenient and popular, giving young people the opportunity to read and discuss books at any time.

Mobile applications significantly ease the learning process for young people. For example, the mobile application "Kitobkhan" is popular among young people, through which users can download and read books of various genres. This application is used as an effective means of promoting reading among young people. The application "Kitobkhan", promoted by the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, serves to connect students with books through modern technologies and is of great importance in developing their reading culture (Azimov, 2018, p. 54).

Also, international platforms such as "Readly" and "Goodreads" allow young people to share their impressions of the books they have read, discover new books, and conduct mutual discussions. Such applications have a positive effect on increasing interest in reading among young people and forming their reading culture (Karimov, 2019, p. 24).

Research and Innovation

Today, scientific approaches and technological innovations are gaining importance in the formation of book reading culture among young people. Modern research is deeply studying the methods of positively influencing the study habits of young people, revealing the importance of innovative technologies in this regard. In particular, the introduction of digital and virtual technologies, such as e-books, audiobooks and virtual reality (VR) technologies, helps to make the learning process more interesting and livelier among young people.

Recent studies have proven the effectiveness of VR and AR technologies in increasing the interest of young people in reading books. For example, VR programs for interactive teaching of historical and artistic works were successfully tested at Samarkand State University. With the help of these software, young people have the opportunity to understand the text in a deeper way than traditional reading, because there is an opportunity to see the characters and events of the story virtually with their own eyes. This approach not only enhances the learning process, but also changes the attitude of young people to study and arouses more interest in acquiring knowledge.

In Uzbekistan, national platforms such as "ZiyoNET" and "Kitob.uz" play an important role in increasing the interest in reading among young people. Through these digital libraries and reading platforms, young people have a wider access to international and national literature, and are able to download and read books in electronic form at any time. At the same time, researches emphasize the high efficiency of audiobooks. Young people often prefer to learn through audiobooks on the go or during other activities, which facilitates the learning process and increases interest in books.

Scientific studies have also noted that innovative technologies help in managing the attention of young people. For example, increasing digital literacy among young people, developing time management and concentration skills is being implemented with the help of technologies. As a result, young people are learning to learn deeply and avoid superficial reading while using technology.

In general, scientific innovations have a great role in the formation of reading culture among young people. With the help of modern technologies, it will make young people interested in studying and provide them with the opportunity to gain deep knowledge. At the same time, the rational use of innovative technologies to attract young people to reading and increase their intellectual potential is an important factor.

Social networks and online platforms also play an important role in increasing interest in reading among young people. In particular, channels such as the "Bookstagram" community on Instagram and the "Book Readers' Club" on Telegram are effective platforms for attracting young people to reading. Through these platforms, users have the opportunity to share opinions about the books they have read, recommend new works, and participate in interesting discussions. For example, on the "Bookstagram" pages, readers can leave comments about books and get acquainted with the opinions of other users, which in turn increases the interest in reading (Usmanov, 2020, p. 15).

National platforms are also playing an important role in this regard. For example, through online platforms provided by the National Library of Uzbekistan, users have the opportunity to read many works of world and national literature in electronic form. This increases the desire to read books among young people and facilitates learning (Rasulov, 2021, p. 31).

Increasing interest in books among young people through mobile applications and online platforms is changing the attitude towards reading. These tools allow readers to read at their own convenience and enrich their thoughts by interacting with other readers. For example, through the "Book club" channels on Telegram, young people have the opportunity to exchange ideas and discuss the books they have read, which increases the pleasure of reading and encourages a deeper understanding of books (Davlatova, 2022, p. 42).

In Uzbekistan, social networks and mobile applications are helping to develop reading culture among young people. For example, the mobile application "Kitobkhan" provides users with various books in electronic form, as well as the opportunity to exchange ideas and conduct discussions among readers (Azimov, 2018, p. 54). Also, channels such as "Bookstagram" pages on Instagram and "Book Club" on Telegram serve to interest young people in reading and unite them. Platforms like these are seen as an important tool in promoting reading to young people.

Mobile applications and social platforms are important tools in increasing the interest of young people in reading. For example, platforms such as Goodreads or Bookstagram allow users to comment on the books they have read, recommend new books, and conduct mutual discussions (Brown, 2019, p. 88). Also, in Uzbekistan, national platforms such as "Kitobkhan" give young people the opportunity to find and discuss reading materials. These platforms are creating new opportunities to increase interest in reading among young people.

Mobile applications and online platforms are of great importance in the development of reading culture among young people. Through these technologies, young people get closer to books, and the culture of reading is formed and expanded among them. At the same time, the

convenience and wide possibilities of new technologies in the process of reading serve as the main factor in increasing interest in reading.

Virtual reality (VR), which is one of the innovative technologies among young people, has made it possible to study in a more realistic way. Through these technologies, it is possible to see the images of the events of the story with one's own eyes, to understand them more deeply. For example, educational programs with VR technology created for students of Samarkand State University allow interactive study of historical and artistic works, which serves to increase their interest in knowledge (Davlatova, 2022, p. 41).

Nowadays, VR and AR technologies are changing the attitude of young people towards reading and encouraging them to read more books. Through these technologies, it is possible to see the characters and events of the book in an interactive form. For example, with the help of modern virtual reality programs, students see the events in the book visually and understand them in a more vivid and interesting way (Garcia, 2022, p. 54). This, in turn, gives a new look to the reading culture of young people and encourages them to understand the text more deeply.

Today, innovative technologies play an important role in increasing interest in reading among young people. Digital libraries, audiobooks, mobile applications and virtual reality (VR) technologies are changing the way young people read books. At the same time, the impact of technologies on the culture of reading is two-sided and has both positive and negative aspects.

Positive effects:

1. Unlimited access to books was created with the help of innovative technologies. With the help of e-libraries and mobile applications, students have the opportunity to read books at the desired place and time, which makes young people more attracted to reading books. In Uzbekistan, platforms such as "ZiyoNET" and "Kitob.uz" present many works of national and world literature for young people, which is of great importance in the development of reading culture (Karimov, 2019, p. 23).

2. E-books and audiobooks play an important role in making the learning process easier and more convenient for young people. With the help of audiobooks, users can spend time studying while on the go, playing sports or doing other activities. Also, the ability to download, re-read and save books in digital format increases interest in reading (Rasulov, 2021, p. 30).

3. Through social platforms, readers can exchange opinions, discuss and recommend the works they have read. For example, Telegram channels such as "Readers' club" are an effective platform for getting young people interested in reading books and developing mutual communication between them. This serves to form reading culture among young people (Usmanov, 2020, p. 15).

Negative effects

1. The proliferation of digital devices and technology can lead to difficulties in attention and concentration among young people. Research shows that using digital devices for a long time leads to distraction and a decrease in concentration. This problem can be solved by developing digital detox and time management skills among young people (Hakimov, 2020, p. 12).

2. The increased use of e-books and audiobooks in many cases can increase dependence on technology. Young people spend more time on mobile devices and risk losing interest in traditional books. This can reduce the ability to understand the book and approach it carefully, especially among young people (Davlatova, 2022, p. 42).

3. Students who use digital technologies often use a quick and superficial reading method, which can prevent them from absorbing knowledge in depth. When using electronic and audio books, there are cases of surface reading or listening to the text, which reduces the possibility of fully accepting the content of the book (Rasulov, 2021, p. 31).

The impact of technology on youth reading is two-sided, with both advantages and disadvantages. Although technology provides unlimited resources for young people, it can reduce their attention and concentration (Evans, 2023, p. 77). Research conducted in this regard shows that young people need to develop self-management skills when using technology (White, 2021, p. 93). Therefore, it is necessary to use effective methods to attract young people to reading, taking into account the specific characteristics of technologies.

Conclusion

Innovative technologies are of particular importance in forming the reading culture of young people. In Uzbekistan, the use of digital libraries, audiobooks, mobile applications and virtual reality technologies are effective tools for attracting young people to reading books. At the same time, taking into account the positive and negative effects of the use of technologies, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at developing the culture of reading among young people. By encouraging young people to read, it is possible to create an educated and intellectually rich society.

Innovative technologies play an important role in the formation of reading culture among young people. E-books, audiobooks, social platforms and virtual reality technologies serve to increase interest in reading among young people. At the same time, targeted education and promotion activities are important to eliminate the negative effects of technology use. The full use of the possibilities of innovative technologies in attracting young people to reading will serve to form an intellectually and culturally rich society in the future. Innovative technologies create great opportunities for increasing interest in reading among young people and simplifying the process of learning. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to the moderate and efficient use of these technologies, to take targeted measures to eliminate the negative effects of technologies. By increasing interest in reading, it is possible to create an intellectually rich and educated young generation.

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